

Development of Accessible, Reproducible Jupyter Notebooks for Education in Nuclear Reactor Engineering

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ABSTRACT

Online and in-person education in nuclear engineering would benefit from the availability of open-source codes and resources. The historical reliance on proprietary software for computations limits access for both students and educators. A general methodology that supports open research objectives is necessary. This work addresses these limitations through the development of a collection of open-source computational notebooks that cover key topics in nuclear reactor analysis by leveraging the interactive nature of Jupyter notebooks and the reproducibility features of Quarto. By hosting the notebooks on a cloud-based platform, easy access and collaboration among learners and instructors are ensured. By combining modern computational tools with open-source practices, this work seeks to enhance the teaching, learning, and dissemination of nuclear reactor analysis concepts, while also supporting transparent and collaborative research principles.

Keywords: education, nuclear engineering, open research, Python, Quarto

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Categories of Nuclear Reactor Computational Platforms

Modern nuclear engineering departments at tertiary education institutes rely on three categories of computational platforms. The first category consists of major integrated codes such as MCNP, Serpent and SCALE. These codes have been developed over many years at national and regional nuclear reactor technology institutes under formal quality management systems. Such codes represent the best available computational technology and are accepted by nuclear safety regulators. Licenses for these codes are strictly controlled and costly. The second category consists of open-source codes for reactor analysis [1]. Two noteworthy platforms are ARMI (Advanced Reactor Modelling Interface) [2] and OpenMC [3]. The third category consists of educational tools, which are not intended for production use but rather for educational purposes. They are often developed in-house by postgraduates and lecturers and far more limited in scope as compared to e.g. OpenMC but can be developed to interface with these platforms and use their functionality. This work focuses on the third category, namely educational tools intended for use within academic institutions, and describes the development and implementation of such tools at North-West University (NWU), South Africa.

At NWU, lecturers often develop computational demonstrations using commercial software not available to students; the students were merely given screen prints or pdf outputs, and had no ability to interact with the code. Cost makes it impossible to procure individual licenses for all students. A need was therefore identified for non-proprietary, license-free educational platforms to teach nuclear reactor analysis principles. A viable solution is the in-house development of a range of educational Jupyter notebooks (JNs) – interactive computational documents which combine executable code, visuals created

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from the code, descriptive text written in Markdown, and embedded $\text{L}^{\text{A}}\text{T}_{\text{E}}\text{X}$ equations. The educational tools, implemented in the form of JNs, are designed to perform realistic reactor analysis computations to bring important facets of nuclear reactor behavior to life. Graduate and postgraduate education in Nuclear Engineering can benefit significantly from the use of computational notebooks, as they promote interactive learning and support the development of physical intuition. Through worked examples, students gain practical insight into the implementation of algebraic and differential equations in code, as well as the generation of graphical outputs and animations. Furthermore, by incorporating open research principles and modern computational tools (discussed in the subsections that follow) students are introduced to both best practices in scientific computing and contemporary methodologies relevant to the field.

1.2. Open Research and Corresponding Software Platforms

The traditional approach to preparing analytical or technical reports, scientific publications, and lecture notes (including codes) in nuclear engineering typically involves several sequential steps: (1) developing calculation models for large-scale codes such as MCNP, Serpent, or SCALE; (2) executing the codes and exporting the output, typically into Excel spreadsheets; (3) using specialized analysis and plotting software to post-process the results and generate tables and figures; and finally, (4) inserting these outputs into MS Word (or other document preparation systems) documents. Such “fragmented and arbitrary” workflows can be error-prone, difficult to reproduce and audit. Using computational notebooks solves this problem by providing an integrated and self-documenting environment that combines definitions, descriptions and mathematical formulæ in LaTeX, with code sections that reads and manipulates the reactor analysis code output, produces graphs and tables and can be rendered to a publishable Word, LaTeX, PDF or HTML document, in which code sections can be electively hidden, depending on the intended audience, thereby better adhering to the so-called open research principles.

Open research, or open science, is a framework that emphasizes transparency, reproducibility, verification and innovation in studies and knowledge distribution to ensure that research is as open as possible [4]. These principles enhance public value, research integrity and reuse throughout the study lifespan. According to [4], science and engineering face a growing replicability crisis, reflected in the increasing number of journal article retractions. This trend has, in turn, stimulated the development of software tools and frameworks aimed at supporting transparent and reproducible research practices. To address these needs, the company Posit has developed the Quarto publishing system, an open-source system for reproducible, open research [5]. Quarto allows authors to use Integrated Development Environments (IDEs) such as JupyterLab, Positron, Visual Studio Code or RStudio (in programming languages such as Python, R, and Julia) to create dynamic documents with embedded code sections. Quarto renders the code into publication-ready, reproducible, professional documents in formats like LaTeX, HTML, PDF, and MS Word, whilst incorporating the use of a journal template, if necessary. Quarto also has the capability to include citations, cross-references and more [5]. By combining code, data, and text into a single document, the ability for others to replicate and verify research findings is promoted. Figure 1 shows the capabilities of Quarto with Jupyter Notebooks developed in this work rendered into HTML format.

1.3. Modern Educational Jupyter Notebooks for Nuclear Reactor Science

Internationally, one of the most popular present-day platform for the development of educational tools is the Python Jupyter Notebook format, by virtue of its interactive computational environment, pleasant user experience and visually appealing interface design. Python’s ease of use, large user community, interoperability, extensive collection of libraries and packages, in combination with the notebook development environment, makes it a good choice for coding. Python offers powerful libraries for physics, mathematics, computations, data analysis and visualization, such as Matplotlib, Seaborn, Plotly, NumPy, SciPy and Pandas [6]. Python packages, specific to nuclear reactors, include RadioAc-

Figure 1. Jupyter notebooks developed in this work and rendered to HTML with Quarto.

tiveDecay [7], whilst OpenMC and ARMI have a Python API (Application Programming Interface). OpenMC and ARMI also host a range of downloadable JNs. Current courses dedicated to teaching reactor physics with JNs include IAEA’s self-paced course [8], training material in chemical engineering at the University of Massachusetts Lowell and also offered as certification at Cortix Tech [9], and the teaching material for the introductory nuclear reactor physics course at the Uppsala University [10].

2. EDUCATIONAL JUPYTER NOTEBOOKS AT NWU

The School of Nuclear Engineering at NWU offers a Postgraduate Diploma (PGDip.) course and several Masters programs. The PGDip. includes modules on Nuclear Engineering I, Radiation and the Environment, Nuclear Reactor Technology, Pressurised Water Reactor (PWR) Technology, Nuclear Project Management, Reactor Safety, Nuclear Energy Policy and Business, and Research Methodology. The structured Masters program includes modules on Nuclear Engineering I and II, Reactor Analysis, Reactor Safety, and Nuclear Project Management. Notebooks are currently used in three of the modules as supplement for lectures and teacher-guided session with intention to also use for homework assignments. The Python-based Jupyter Notebooks developed in this work are created and maintained in Visual Studio Code, leveraging its integrated development environment and rich ecosystem of extensions to support efficient development and maintenance. They are considered to be the starting point of the future collection to be used in modules where applicable, by the lecturers as supporting material and by the students enrolled for such modules. The selected topics were chosen to provide learners with a structured progression from fundamental nuclear reactor principles to more advanced nuclear reactor dynamics. The notebooks developed so far are briefly discussed in the following subsections.

2.1. Prompt Fission Neutron (PFN) Energy Spectra

A dense population of free neutrons move through a nuclear reactor core, driving the self-sustaining fission chain reaction. The population of free neutrons is produced by fission. More than 99% of such fission neutrons are released immediately following fission and are therefore known as Prompt Fission

Neutrons (PFNs). The PFN energy spectra can be described by the Watt distribution. They are born at average energies of ≈ 2 MeV and are deliberately moderated and thermalized in thermal neutron spectrum reactors. PFNs represent the primary source that sustains the population of free neutrons in a reactor core and the neutron fluence rate that leaks out of the reactor. This leakage requires biological shielding and shielding to protect structures and components against excessive neutron activation and radiation damage. The accuracy of reactor analysis calculations depends directly on the accuracy with which PFN emission spectra are modelled, and inaccuracies can impact integral parameters such as the neutron multiplication factor, k_{eff} , by hundreds of pcm (per cent mille) [11]. This notebook focusses on the analysis and visualization of PFN emission spectra for important fissile actinides and one spontaneously fissioning isotope by having implemented the Watt distribution formula, and this will enable students to investigate a range of topics such as calculating average neutron emission energies.

2.2. Maxwell-Boltzmann Energy Distribution of Thermal Neutrons

Neutrons are released with high energies and lose their energy through collisions until they reach a state of thermal equilibrium with the medium. The velocity and energy distributions of such neutrons are described by the well-known Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. Thermal neutron spectrum reactors use moderators to get neutrons to reach this equilibrium distribution more efficiently. At thermal neutron energies, the cross-section of neutron-induced fission of fissile actinides such as ^{235}U is significantly larger than at the higher neutron energies at which PFNs are “born” [11]. This principle explains the dominance of thermal reactors in the current nuclear power landscape [12]. Understanding and modelling neutron thermalization is key in reactor analysis. This notebook shows this concept by having implemented the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, and this will enable students to visualize the impact of moderator temperature on the thermal neutron spectrum.

2.3. The Ingrowth of the ^{235}U , ^{238}U and ^{232}Th Radioactive Decay Series

Three dominant radioactive decay chains, that are often of interest in the front end of the nuclear fuel cycle, for example in mining and nuclear fuel fabrication, are the ^{238}U , ^{235}U and ^{232}Th series. The continual production of the radioactive gas radon ^{222}Rn , a progeny nuclide in the ^{238}U decay series, is often a significant radiological safety concern. The evolution of radionuclide activities in these series is described by sets of coupled linear Ordinary Differential Equations (ODE), known as the Bateman equations. It is necessary to visualize the time evolution of series ingrowth of the radioactive transition cascades and to quantify the ionizing photon dose rates of individual nuclides in the ^{238}U , ^{235}U and ^{232}Th series. The notebook focuses on radionuclide decay by using the Python package RadioActiveDecay [7] and will enable learners to visually and numerically explore the time evolution of the activities of progeny nuclides as well as the unshielded photon dose rate from a point source, thus illustrating the need for biological shielding around reactors.

2.4. Neutron Group Cross-Section Collapsing

The use of continuous-energy neutron cross-section data is well established as a means of accurately representing neutron interaction behaviour. However, such high-fidelity treatment is computationally demanding and may result in significant execution times. Collapsing, or averaging, continuous-energy cross-sections into a limited number of broad energy groups using an appropriate neutron spectrum reduces computational complexity while maintaining acceptable accuracy for many reactor analysis applications. Particularly challenging cross-sections are those of actinide isotopes such as ^{235}U and ^{238}U , which exhibit thousands of resonance peaks. To illustrate this approach, this notebook collapses the cross-section data of ^{235}U into a user-defined multigroup partition of the neutron energy interval $E_n \in [10^{-11}; 20]$ MeV, by employing OpenMC's `openmc.mgxs` module. This module calculates the flux-weighted multi-group microscopic cross-sections for most neutron cross-sections [3, 13]. In the

(a) Neutron flux spectrum in a VVER

(b) Continuous and spectrum-collapsed cross-sections

 Figure 2. Notebook example of collapsing the microscopic fission cross-section of ^{235}U to three energy groups.

OpenMC workflow, NJOY is used as a pre-processor to convert evaluated nuclear data libraries (e.g., ENDF/B, JEFF, or TENDL) from their raw formats into linear-linear interpolable ACE libraries at discrete material temperatures. OpenMC then converts these ACE libraries into its native HDF5 format for use in transport simulations. Figure 2 illustrates the microscopic fission cross-section of ^{235}U collapsed to three energy groups, as generated by the notebook. Working with this notebook will give students experience at invoking OpenMC functionality from within JNs. In addition, this will open the door to a wide range of postgraduate projects based on reactor analyses using OpenMC.

2.5. The Multi-Timescale Point Reactor Model

Nuclear reactor kinetics addresses the short-term time-dependent behavior of a reactor (milliseconds to minutes) in response to operational or accidental perturbations. Dynamic reactivity feedback, driven by changes in temperature, coolant flow, and other reactor conditions, plays a critical role in governing the balance between neutron production and loss, thereby influencing reactor stability. Over longer time scales, processes such as fuel burnup, transmutation, and fission product poisoning modify key neutronic parameters, including the multiplication factor, reactivity coefficients, and kinetic parameters, further affecting reactor behavior. Combining short, medium and long-term processes in one modelling tool would result therefore in “a code with the unique capability of modelling transients at any time during a fuel cycle” [14].

In this work, a JN with these capabilities has been developed. The short-term kinetics is captured using the standard point reactor kinetics equations, while medium and long-term dynamics involve integrating fuel burnup equations with the point kinetic model. In each case, the system is modeled with a set of ODEs. These equations are challenging to solve due to the varying time scales involved, leading to what is known as a “stiff system”, thus requiring specialized numerical methods [15]. In our work, these ODEs are solved using SciPy’s function `solve_ivp`, often utilising the LSODA solver which utilises the Adams/BDF method with automatic stiffness detection and switching [16].

2.5.1. Short timescale kinetic behavior (seconds to minutes)

A reactor is simulated using the standard point kinetics model with an arbitrary (typically one-, six or eight) families of delayed neutrons and is extended with a simplified thermal-hydraulic (fuel-to-coolant heat transfer) to model reactivity feedback. This framework demonstrates the development of a reactor point kinetic model formulated as a coupled system of ODEs to simulate the dynamic response of reactor power, fuel temperature, and coolant temperature to externally imposed reactivity perturba-

Figure 3. Simulation of a transient in a PWR in response to an external perturbation of 14.5 cents.

tions [15]. Figure 3a illustrates the calculated response to an external perturbation of 14.5 cents, and 3b shows the power-to-reactivity frequency response magnitude. Model parameters, used to represent a standard PWR, correspond to the H. B. Robinson PWR, with typical values and operating conditions drawn from [17, 15]. It is worth noting, that the developed system allows incorporating delayed photoneutrons into the kinetic model. Photoneutrons can be produced in (γ, n) and (γ, f) reactions, especially in nuclear reactors containing D_2O or Be [18]. As illustration, Figure 4, shows examples from [18] reproduced in the notebook. Figure 4a shows the neutron density of delayed neutrons and photoneutrons for a reactivity, which is dependent on time, t , and neutron density, n , as $\rho = at - b \int_0^t n(t') dt'$, for different values of parameters a and b . In this formula, a is the external reactivity insertion rate and b is the feedback (shutdown) reactivity coefficient. Figure 4b shows the neutron density of delayed neutrons and photoneutrons for an oscillatory (sinusoidal) reactivity perturbation $\rho(t) = a \sin(t/\tau)$, where the magnitude of external reactivity insertion, a (in dollars), and the oscillation period, τ , are known constants. All other parameters, used in these examples, are taken from [18].

2.5.2. Medium timescale dynamics (hours to days)

Here, the primary focus is on reactor poisoning and decay heat phenomena. Among the various fission products that cause reactor poisoning, ^{135}Xe is of significant concern due to its very large absorption cross-section for thermal neutrons ($\sigma_a \approx 3.5 \times 10^6$ b). The fission product poisoning phenomenon is incorporated into the point kinetics model by tracking the relevant nuclides using the Bateman equations [14]. Main sources of decay heat production, after a nuclear reactor has been shut down, are the actinides created by radiative capture, delayed radioactive decay of fission products, and activated structural materials produced by radiative capture [11]. The decay heat phenomenon was integrated into our point kinetics model by including experimental data provided by the American Nuclear Society's decay heat standards [14, 19].

2.5.3. Long timescale dynamics (up to years)

Transmutation processes, in which neutrons transform fissionable isotopes like ^{238}U into fissile ^{239}Pu , naturally affects reactor performance. This is primarily due to the evolving delayed neutron fraction, β . The transmutation effect is incorporated into the standard point kinetics model by updating the delayed neutron fractions (β_i), where index i corresponds to ^{235}U , ^{239}Pu , and ^{238}U , using a weighted average approach to compute the new delayed neutron fraction, as described in [14].

Figure 4. Evolution of the density of delayed- and photoneutrons (Reproduced from the examples given in [18]).

3. ONLINE HOSTING OF EDUCATIONAL JUPYTER NOTEBOOKS

In order to promote accessibility, the developed JNs are designed to be platform-independent and be hosted on a cloud-based infrastructure to support both online and in-person teaching. The selection of an appropriate hosting platform was guided by several key criteria: it should be freely accessible, provide version-controlled storage, enable code execution, support collaborative workflows, and offer a user-friendly interface. To the authors' knowledge, no single platform satisfies all of these requirements. Drawing on established practices for hosting computational notebooks in the nuclear engineering community (e.g., projects such as OpenMC and ARMI), GitHub has been selected as the primary platform. GitHub is widely used for hosting, managing, and collaborating on code due to its free public repositories, robust version control capabilities, integrated project management tools, support for collaborative development, extensive open-source community, and seamless integration with numerous integrated development environments (IDEs). In addition, GitHub Pages enables repositories to be deployed as websites, providing a more user-friendly and professional presentation. Through GitHub Pages, content rendered locally using Quarto can be published as a static website, thereby improving accessibility and dissemination – which was an essential requirement for our project.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The historical reliance on proprietary software as the primary educational and computational platform for modelling and training in nuclear reactor engineering at the NWU imposes several constraints, including the high cost of- and limited access to software licences. Such limitations are not unique to this institution but are widely experienced across the academic community. A collection of computational Jupyter Notebooks is being developed to enable students to interact with fundamental reactor analysis concepts. Furthermore, education in computational nuclear reactor analysis is frequently hindered by the difficulty of reproducing published results, owing to unavailable, inaccessible, or insufficiently documented codes. Transitioning to Python-based Jupyter notebooks, rendering document-equivalent outputs using Quarto, and hosting the notebooks on an appropriate online platform promotes accessibility, transparency, and reproducibility of computational workflows.

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